

Five-year trends of antimicrobial drugs consumption and incidence of bloodstream infections caused by multidrug-resistant pathogens in a Greek ICU

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Summary

Excessive and inappropriate use of antibiotics enhances the emergence of antimicrobial resistance, resulting into a vicious cycle. Continuous surveillance of antibiotic consumption and implementation of antibiotic stewardship programs (ASP) is an important component of infection control interventions. Greece is a high endemicity area for multidrug resistant pathogens (MDR), especially carbapenem-resistant (CR) Gram-negatives (GN), and moreover antibiotic consumption is among the highest in Europe. Aim of this study was to record antibiotic consumption and the incidence of bloodstream infections (BSI) caused by MDR pathogens in our 12-bed general ICU, before initiating an ASP in the hospital. Trends over time were also evaluated.

An observational study was performed from January 2010 to December 2014. Consumption data were retrospectively collected from the hospital pharmacy records and expressed as daily defined doses (DDD) per 1000 patient-days (PD). All BSI episodes caused by CR *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKP), CR *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB), CR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CRPA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* spp (VRE) and methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) were prospectively recorded. Identification was performed by conventional or automated methods (Vitek 2 Compact, bioMerieux). Antimicrobial susceptibility testing and MIC values determination was performed by Vitek 2 and Etest (bioMerieux).

We recorded 395 BSI episodes caused by the study pathogens, with a mean annual incidence of 21.21/1000 PD. The incidence declined from 22.95 in 2011 to 17.90/1000 PD in 2013, however, a significant increase was observed in 2014 (25.21/1000 PD, $p=0.03$). No correlations between the consumption of antimicrobial agents (AMA) and incidence data were found. The predominant pathogens were CRAB and CRKP. Antibiotic use was high in all 5 years of the study with a mean annual consumption of 3077 DDD/1000 PD. The most common AMA prescribed was ampicillin/sulbactam (17.7%), followed by meropenem (16.8%) and colistin (11.8%). The total AMA consumption rose by 20.3% from 2010 to 2014 ($p=0.18$). The rate of change in AMA use was more remarkable for quinolones (128.4%, $p=0.004$) and colistin (66.1%, $p=0.02$). A decreasing trend was observed for only few antimicrobials, such as tigecycline (-48.5%, $p=0.12$) and daptomycin (-93%, $p=0.012$). Total AMA use temporarily decreased in 2011 (-21.3%, $p=0.33$) and a continuous and significant increasing trend was observed thereafter ($p=0.022$).

In conclusion, the local epidemiology of resistance defines the antimicrobial decision-making. In our setting, the high incidence of CRGN imposes the use of broad-spectrum and last resort AMA. In the era of growing resistance and limited treatment options, judicious antibiotic use is crucial. Our surveillance data increase our awareness and necessitate the ASP launching, so as to optimize antibiotic prescribing and preserve the effectiveness of last resort antimicrobials.

Key words

antibiotic surveillance, antimicrobial use, consumption of antimicrobials, antibiotic stewardship, intensive care unit, carbapenem resistance, multidrug-resistant pathogens

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Introduction

The emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance is a growing public health threat and a daily challenge in clinical practice.¹ Intensive Care Unit (ICU) settings can be considered as “reservoirs” for multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens.² The development of resistant flora can occur by importation of resistant strains from newly admitted patients, by cross-transmission of resistant strains via the hands of healthcare workers or the environment and by selection of resistant pathogens because of antimicrobial overuse or misuse.³ Inadequate coverage, excessive spectrum, ineffective dosing, non-optimal route and undue treatment duration are all considered inappropriate use.⁴

ICUs provide care for critically ill patients, who are diagnosed with a serious infection or are more prone for developing a new one due to multiple comorbidities and invasive procedures. Therefore, antimicrobial agents (AMA) are often employed as treatment or prophylaxis to contain morbidity and mortality.⁵ Resistance, inevitably, impacts antibiotic prescribing and vice versa. Physicians use broad-spectrum antibiotics and the vicious cycle of further resistance, conferred by selection pressure, is

dequate coverage, excessive spectrum, ineffective dosing, non-optimal route and undue treatment duration are all considered inappropriate use.⁴

perpetuated while effective options are limited, resulting into high mortality rates from MDR infections.⁵⁻⁶

In Greece, antimicrobial resistance rates and antibiotic consumption are among the highest in Europe.⁷ More precisely, according to the ECDC surveillance report of hospital-acquired infections and antimicrobial use in European acute care hospitals (ECDC PPS-HAIs), the prevalence of antimicrobial use in Greek hospitals is 54.7%, reported as the highest in Europe.⁸ Noteworthy, Greek hospitals also rank first in the consumption of last-line antibiotics, such as polymyxins and tigecycline. The prevalence of carbapenem-resistant (CR) Gram-negative pathogens (GN) is considerably high, including endemic strains in ICUs and increasingly resistant strains from community-onset infections.⁷⁻⁸

Studies have shown that up to 60% of antibiotics prescribed in clinical practice, even in the ICU, are unnecessary, inappropriate, or suboptimal.² The contemporary challenge is to cure bacterial diseases with minimal ecological impact.⁴ In response to that, the universal concern in the infection-control community has prompted the provision of antimicrobial stewardship interventions, which are increasingly being advocated as an important strategy to increase the appropriateness of antibiotic prescribing, aiming to prevent the development and spread of antimicrobial resistance, improve patients' outcomes and reduce the healthcare costs.^{2,4,9-12} Considering the vicious cycle of resistance, the launch of rapid diagnostics for the fast identification of pathogens and thus immediate intervention and the use of biomarkers for the differential diagnosis of septic episodes, represent the cornerstones of antibiotic stewardship programs (ASP) in the ICUs.^{2,13}

In our hospital, in response to the increasing needs to contain antibiotic resistance, improve clinical outcomes and reduce costs associated with inappropriate antimicrobial consumption, along with other interventions, we have recently designed and intend to implement an ASP. In order to prioritize our efforts and accurately assess the impact of the ASP, it is necessary to provide baseline data on antibiotic consumption and to estimate the burden of infections caused by MDR resistant pathogens.

The present study is the report of the pre-implementation phase. Our aim was to record antibiotic consumption and the incidence of bloodstream infections (BSI) caused by MDR pathogens in our ICU, during 2010-2014.

Methods

An observational study was performed during a five-year period (1/1/2010-31/12/2014) in the 12-bed combined medical-surgical ICU of Tzaneio General Hospital

of Piraeus, a 426-bed tertiary care hospital, located in Attica, Greece.

The patients admitted in the ICU during the study period were included as the study population. All BSI episodes (documented by positive blood culture and consistent clinical presentation) caused by methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* spp (VRE), CR *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKP), CR *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB) and CR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CRPA) were prospectively recorded. For patients with multiple episodes of BSI, repeated episodes were recorded if they were caused by a different pathogen or occurred at least 15 days after the last positive blood culture. Incidence rates were calculated for all MDR pathogens and for each of them separately and were expressed as the number of episodes per 1000 patient-days (PD).

Blood cultures were incubated in BACTEC 9240 Automated Blood Culture System (Becton and Dickinson, New Jersey, USA). Identification was performed by conventional or automated methods (Vitek 2 Compact, bioMerieux, Marcy l'Etoile, France). Antimicrobial susceptibility testing and MIC values determination were performed by Vitek 2 and Etest (bioMerieux). CRKP and CRPA isolates were further tested for underlying carbapenem resistance mechanisms by phenotypic assays (combined disk tests with meropenem and imipenem respectively, with the addition of carbapenemase inhibitors).¹⁴⁻¹⁵

Antibiotic consumption data were collected retrospectively from the hospital pharmacy records. These data were analyzed according to the Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System of the World Health Organization (WHO).¹⁶ The following antibiotics were examined: carbapenems, ampicillin/sulbactam, piperacillin/tazobactam, 3rd and 4th generation cephalosporins, aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, colistin, tigecycline, glycopeptides, macrolides, metronidazole and linezolid. Antimicrobial use was expressed as daily defined doses (DDD) per 1000 PD.

Data regarding hospital activity (admissions, number of PD in full hospitalization) were obtained from hospital administration.

All statistical analyses were performed by using the SPSS statistical software (version 20; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL). Rates of change in antibiotic consumption were determined as changes in the number of DDD per 1000 PD during the study period. Linear regression with the yearly data was carried out to analyze the trends in antibiotic consumption over time. Pearson's correlation was applied to determine the correlation between antibiotic consumption and annual incidence of BSI caused by MDR pathogens. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

A total of 454 patients were admitted in the ICU during the period under review. Patients' stay in ICU ranged from two to 629 days. We recorded 395 BSI episodes caused by the study pathogens, with a mean incidence of 21.21/1000 PD in all 5 years of the study. The annual incidence of BSI caused by MDR pathogens and the pathogen-specific BSI annual incidence per 1000 PD are presented in Figure 1. The incidence of BSI caused by MDR pathogens declined, albeit not significantly, from 22.95/1000 PD in 2011 to 17.90 in 2013 ($p=0.12$), however, a significant increase was observed in 2014 (25.21/1000 PD, $p=0.03$). No correlations between AMA consumption and incidence data were found. The predominant pathogens in all 5 years were CRAB and CRKP, with the latter prevailing in 2012-2013. The rate of colistin resistance among CRKP was 36%.

All patients in our study received antibiotic regimens either for prophylactic or therapeutic use. In total we recorded 57,298.5 DD with a mean 11,459.7 DDD per year. The most common AMA prescribed was ampicillin/sulbactam (17.7%), followed by meropenem (16.8%), colistin (11.8%), teicoplanin (10%), ciprofloxacin (6.2%), piperacillin/tazobactam (6.1%) and tigecycline (5.6%). When considering the class of AMA, β -lactams/ β -lactamase inhibitors (23.7%) and carbapenems (18.8%) were maximally used, followed by glycopeptides (10.2%), fluoroquinolones (9.4%) and extended-spectrum cephalosporins (8.6%).

Antibiotic consumption per 1000 PD during the 5 years of the study is presented in Table 1 and Figure 2. The consumption rose by 20.3 % from 2010 (3063.1 DDD/1000 PD) to 2014 (3683.8 DDD/1000 PD), but this change was not statistically significant ($p=0.18$). The trend of total antimicrobial use is presented in Figure 2. Considering the annual quantitative utilization of AMA, total use temporarily decreased in 2011 (rate of change -21.3%, $p=0.33$) and a continuous and significant increasing trend was observed thereafter ($p=0.022$). Most antimicrobials followed this trend with few exceptions. The consumption trend over time for the main classes of AMA is presented in Figures 3 and 4.

The rate of change in AMA consumption between 2010 and 2014 (Table 1) was more remarkable for quinolones, with their use rising more than one-fold (rate of change 128.4%, $p=0.004$), colistin (66.1%, $p=0.02$), extended spectrum cephalosporins (88.3%, $p=0.07$), piperacillin/tazobactam (49.1%, $p=0.12$) and glycopeptides (55.5% $p=0.45$). Colistin use presented a continuous increase from 2010 (256.61 DDD/1000 PD) to 2014 (426.21 DDD/1000 PD) and the same pat-

tern was noted for fluoroquinolones (from 186.42 to 425.68 DDD/1000 PD).

A decreasing trend in consumption was observed for only few antimicrobials. Tigecycline consumption was reduced almost to half from 2010 to 2014 (-48.5%, $p=0.12$), declining from 239.13 to 123.16 DDD/1000 PD. Daptomycin consumption was limited, especially after 2012 (-93%, $p=0.012$). Consumption of aztreonam, though low, was also decreased (-97.4%, $p=0.09$). For aminoglycosides, a slight decrease was noted (-15.9%) between 2010 and 2014. Gentamicin was used more frequently, compared with amikacin during the study period, with the exception of 2011, when the lowest use of gentamicin was observed (43.86 DDD/1000 PD, rate of change -66.4%).

Significant variations over time were observed for linezolid. Its use decreased from 152.03 DDD/1000 PD in 2010 to 50.72 DDD/1000 PD in 2012 ($p=0.011$), slightly increased in 2013 (68.24 DDD/1000 PD and almost doubled in 2014 (128.68 DDD/1000 PD, $p=0.003$) reaching the high consumption levels of 2010.

Carbapenems' consumption (mainly meropenem) was high during the study period and did not differ between 2010 and 2014 (rate of change 1%). However, their use significantly decreased in 2011 (from 594.5 to 468.4 DDD/1000 PD, $p=0.024$) and reached the maximum of 694.44 DDD/1000 PD in 2013.

Fosfomycin was not routinely used and it was only administered in a few cases of pan-drug resistant infections. The use of anti-anaerobic agents was also limited.

Discussion

Antibiotic use varies from hospital to hospital and among different departments of the same hospital, in relation to the patients' needs.¹⁷ In ICU, patients are 5 to 10 times more prone to develop nosocomial infections, resistance rates are higher, antibiotic use is among the highest in the hospital and appropriate treatment selection is complex.^{2,18} Antimicrobial stewardship, including appropriate selection, dosing, route and duration of antimicrobial therapy targets to both better clinical outcomes and lower risk for resistance development.⁴ However, several difficulties have been identified in improving prescribing and implementing an ASP in ICU settings, although the addition of rapid diagnostics and biomarkers could optimize the results.^{2,13,19-21}

In this study we report our data on antibiotic consumption and on the incidence of BSI caused by MDR pathogens (CRGN, MRSA and VRE) in our ICU during 2010-2014. BSI represented the majority of all infec-

Figure 1 Incidence (per 1000 PD) of BSI episodes caused by CRGN, VRE and MRSA, during the study period (2010-2014). CRGN, carbapenem-resistant Gram-negatives (*K. pneumoniae*, *A. baumannii* and *P. aeruginosa*); VRE, vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus*; MRSA, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*; MDRO, multidrug-resistant organisms (CRGN and VRE and MRSA)

Figure 2 Antibiotic consumption (DDD/1000 PD) per antimicrobial group, during the study period

Table 1 Annual consumption of antimicrobials (2010-2014) and comparison of antimicrobial use between 2010 and 2014

	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	change%	p
Antimicrobials (DDD/1000 PD)							
Piperacillin/tazobactam	175.90	122.39	178.34	198.18	262.34	49.14	0.12
Ampicillin/Sulbactam	668.94	438.81	377.89	635.15	601.63	-10.06	0.17
β-lactames/β-lactamase inhibitors combinations	844.84	561.19	556.23	833.33	863.97	2.26	0.61
Ceftriaxone	93.49	15.55	189.08	215.28	263.66	182.01	0.06
Ceftazidime	0.85	0.00	0.00	1.60	1.84	115.63	0.23
Cefepime	100.60	113.72	128.45	95.62	101.63	1.03	0.76
Extended spectrum cephalosporines (total)	194.94	129.27	317.53	312.50	367.12	88.32	0.07
Aztreonam	50.01	65.27	20.12	33.12	1.31	-97.37	0.09
Meropenem	554.42	432.94	437.43	631.41	532.56	-3.94	0.63
Imipenem	40.07	35.44	100.88	63.03	68.01	69.75	0.39
Ertapenem	0.00	0.00	4.13	0.00	0.00		1
Carbapenems (total)	594.49	468.38	542.45	694.44	600.58	1.02	0.44
Moxifloxacin	31.54	45.13	49.06	34.19	35.19	11.56	0.9
Ciprofloxacin	85.54	171.85	183.57	235.74	276.26	222.98	0.004
Levofloxacin	69.34	20.65	31.70	61.16	114.23	64.75	0.32
Quinolones (total)	186.42	237.63	264.33	331.09	425.68	128.35	0.004
Amikacin	53.42	56.48	20.67	28.31	49.50	-7.34	0.56
Gentamicin	130.43	43.86	179.99	135.42	108.72	-16.65	0.81
Netilmicin	4.26	9.43	2.21	0.00	0.00	-100.00	0.17
Aminoglycosides (total)	188.12	109.77	202.87	163.73	158.22	-15.90	0.97
Teicoplanin	310.88	209.59	335.17	203.26	481.36	54.83	0.43
Vancomycin	2.13	11.35	10.75	0.00	5.25	146.43	0.8
Glycopeptides (total)	313.02	220.93	345.92	203.26	486.61	55.46	0.45
Linezolid	152.03	90.26	50.72	68.24	128.68	-15.36	0.67
Daptomycin	80.70	49.57	21.78	9.35	5.65	-93.00	0.012
Colistin	256.61	349.31	377.07	401.98	426.21	66.09	0.016
Tigecycline	239.13	173.51	230.15	104.83	123.16	-48.50	0.12
Fosfomycin	0.00	0.00	20.40	1.87	12.87		0.42
Metronidazole	12.79	20.40	40.24	15.22	23.11	80.71	0.72
Clindamycin	0.00	0.00	62.84	61.97	61.97		0.06
Azithromycin	0.00	0.00	13.51	0.00	0.00		
Total	3063.09	2410.22	3046.03	3201.82	3683.82	20.27	0.18

Figure 3 Consumption of the main classes of antimicrobials (DDD/1000 PD) during the study period

Figure 4 Consumption of last line antimicrobials (DDD/1000 PD) during the study period

tions registered and thus best reflected the infection burden in this setting. Furthermore, it is a life-threatening infection accounting for an important amount of the antimicrobials administered in the ICU. CRGN are endemic in our ICU, in accordance with the data

of the European Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance Network (EARS-Net) that consider Greece at an endemic stage since 2010.²² In our ICU, the prevalence of carbapenem resistance among *K. pneumoniae* blood isolates during the study period was 97%, whereas

the carbapenem resistance rate for *A. baumannii* is almost 100%.

The incidence of BSI caused by MDR pathogens in 2014 did not differ from that observed in 2010. However, due to a successful infection control bundle targeting CRGN, a decreasing trend was recorded in 2011-2013, when a lower incidence for CRGN was noted; the incidence rose significantly in 2014, mostly due to the significantly higher incidence of CRKP and CRAB; this increase is possibly attributed to difficulties in bundle implementation. The increasing trend of CRKP seems to be in line with recent publications from Italy which faces an endemic situation too.²³⁻²⁴ CRKP and CRAB have now overtaken CRPA as the leading pathogens responsible for BSI. The low incidence of CRPA is consistent with national data (www.keel-pno.gr/prokroustis) and may be related to the heavy use of colistin, which retains excellent activity against *P. aeruginosa*. The prevalence of Gram-positive MDR pathogens was relatively low in our study, especially for MRSA, with a total of 4 BSI episodes during the five years. In fact, *S. aureus* ranks tenth as causative agent of hospital acquired infections in Greece, according to the ECDC PPS-HAIs, whereas it is the second most frequent pathogen in Europe. *Enterococcus* spp is among the five more common pathogens in both Greece and Europe, however, VRE isolates are not quite prevalent in our country.⁸

Antibiotic use in our ICU was high in all 5 years of the study, with a mean annual consumption of 3077 DDD/1000 PD to be recorded. Our data are not surprising as it is well-documented that the prevalence of antimicrobial use in Greek hospitals is the highest in Europe.⁸ Important diversity between the results from different countries exists in the available literature on antibiotic use. This variation could be the product of divergences regarding the susceptibility rates or not consistent metrics.¹⁷ Antibiotic use could also vary because of significant differences in the patient population (patient-mix) regarding underlying diseases or comorbidities. Consequently, interhospital comparisons of antimicrobial consumption cannot be easily made due to the complexity of the methods applied and of the variables of interest.¹⁷ Antibiotic consumption in our ICU was considerably higher (almost double) compared with data presented in a recent systematic review¹⁸ and more than two-fold higher than that reported from 98 German ICUs.²⁵ It is also over two-fold higher than the median of 1254 DDD/1000 PD reported in a European ICU multicenter surveillance program.²⁶ However, the severity of illness (case-mix) in our setting may have, somehow, contributed to the observed considerably higher consumption.¹⁷ Patients admitted in Greek ICUs are often

more severely ill due to the delay in the process of finding an ICU-bed, as the availability of ICU-beds is limited and waiting lists are long.

Regarding the trend of antimicrobial consumption over time, total antimicrobial use increased by 20.3% between 2010 and 2014, however a temporal reduction was noted in 2011. This decrease is not consistent with the higher incidence of MDR BSI in 2011, compared with 2010. Furthermore, the AMA consumption and BSI incidence cannot also be correlated the following two years; although a lower incidence was observed, due to the infection control bundle we have implemented, a higher AMA use was recorded. In 2014, both BSI incidence and AMA use were the highest. Nevertheless, it is quite difficult to correlate CR infections' rates and antibiotic consumption, as the incidence highly depends on the preventive measures and the rate of compliance with them. Increasing trends in antibiotic consumption have been also reported by other recent studies.²⁷ Regarding German ICUs, in an 11-year period study, the total antibiotic use increased over time and so did the resistance rates.²⁵

In our ICU, the most commonly used antibiotics for Gram-negative pathogens were ampicillin/sulbactam (17.7%), meropenem (16.8%) and colistin (11.8%), followed by ciprofloxacin (6.2%), piperacillin/ tazobactam (6.1%) and tigecycline (5.6%). The extensive use of ampicillin/sulbactam could be attributed to its administration as empiric therapy alone or in combination to other AMA for CRAB infections, despite the very low susceptibility rates. The high consumption of carbapenem and colistin is mainly due to their use in combination schemes for the treatment of CRKP infections.^{6,28} A significantly increasing trend in colistin consumption was observed, which, however, resulted in high rates of colistin resistance among CRKP isolates. The decreasing trend of tigecycline use may be related to the fact that this agent doesn't reach high concentrations in blood and consequently it is not ideal as monotherapy for the treatment of BSI, which represent the predominant infections in our setting.²⁹ Pricing issues may have also contributed to the observed reduction. The elevated consumption of gentamicin compared with amikacin can be explained by the predominance of KPC-producing *K. pneumoniae* strains, usually susceptible to gentamicin.⁶ Availability of certain compounds in hospital's inventory may have also influenced these findings.

Teicoplanin (10%) and linezolid (3.2%) were the most frequently used anti-Gram-positive agents. Considering the low incidence of BSI caused by MRSA and VRE in our study and the low prevalence of these pathogens in Greek ICUs,^{7,8} this use seems to be questio-

nable; moreover, the extensive use of linezolid has contributed to the emergence and spread of linezolid-resistant *Staphylococcus epidermidis* isolates in Greek hospitals.³⁰

A considerable heterogeneity of the antibiotic consumption by antibiotic classes is observed in the literature, as expected. In German ICUs, penicillins (24%) and cephalosporins (19.1%) were the most frequently used AMA classes, followed by carbapenems (13.7%) and fluoroquinolones (13.4%).²⁵ A multicenter point prevalence study including data from 88 ICUs located in 12 countries in Southeastern Europe, Turkey and Iran, reported carbapenems (30.2%), anti-Gram positive agents (25.9%), β -lactam/ β -lactamase inhibitors (25.6%) and extended-spectrum cephalosporins (23.9%) as the most commonly used antimicrobials.³¹ In the USA, vancomycin, piperacillin/tazobactam and meropenem were reported as the most frequently prescribed empiric antibiotics in 67 ICUs of 32 different hospitals.³² In a recently published study from Vietnam, a lower middle-income country with high carbapenem resistance rates, 3rd generation cepha-

losporins (20.1%), fluoroquinolones (19.4%) and carbapenems (14.1%) were the most common antimicrobials used in 15 different ICUs.³³ Data regarding antibiotic utilization in Europe also reveal significant variation among countries; it is not surprising that a high prevalence of carbapenem use was observed in Greece and the prevalence of polymyxins and tigecycline use was the highest (3.2%).⁸

It is plausible that the local epidemiology of resistance defines the antimicrobial decision-making. In our setting, the high incidence of CRGN imposes the use of broad-spectrum and last resort AMA in the critically ill patients. This use, however, could contribute to the emergence of further drug resistance creating a vicious cycle that endangers the effectiveness of infectious diseases treatment. In the era of growing resistance and limited treatment options, judicious antibiotic use is crucial.³⁴ Our surveillance data allow benchmarking and assessment of our policies, increase our awareness and highlight the urgent need to implement an ASP, so as to optimize antibiotic prescribing and preserve the effectiveness of last resort antimicrobials.

Περίληψη

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Εξέλιξη της κατανάλωσης αντιβιοτικών και της επίπτωσης των βακτηριακών που προκαλούνται από πολυανθεκτικά παθογόνα σε ΜΕΘ κατά τη διάρκεια μιας πενταετίας

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Η υπερβολική και λανθασμένη χρήση αντιβιοτικών προάγει την ανάπτυξη αντοχής και οδηγεί σε ένα φαύλο κύκλο. Η εφαρμογή προγραμμάτων επιτήρησης κατανάλωσης και ορθολογικής χρήσης αντιβιοτικών (ΕΚΟΧΑ) αποτελεί σημαντική συνιστώσα των παρεμβάσεων για τον έλεγχο των λοιμώξεων. Η Ελλάδα αποτελεί ενδημική περιοχή για τα πολυανθεκτικά παθογόνα και ιδιαίτερα για τα ανθεκτικά στις καρβαπενέμες (CR) Gram-αρνητικά (GN), ενώ ταυτόχρονα παρουσιάζει την υψηλότερη κατανάλωση αντιβιοτικών στην Ευρώπη. Σκοπός της μελέτης ήταν να καταγραφεί η κα-

τανάλωση αντιβιοτικών, καθώς και η επίπτωση των βακτηριακών (BSI) που προκαλούνται από πολυανθεκτικά παθογόνα στη ΜΕΘ του νοσοκομείου μας, πριν την έναρξη ενός προγράμματος ΕΚΟΧΑ. Επίσης αναλύθηκε η εξέλιξη των τάσεων τόσο της κατανάλωσης, όσο και της επίπτωσης κατά τη διάρκεια της πενταετούς (2010-2014) μελέτης.

Πραγματοποιήθηκε μελέτη παρατήρησης από 1/1/2010 έως 31/12/2014. Τα δεδομένα της κατανάλωσης συγκεντρώθηκαν αναδρομικά από τα αρχεία του φαρμακείου και εκφράστηκαν ως "daily defined doses" (DDD) ανά 1000 ασθενονήμερες (PD). Καταγράφηκαν προοπτικά όλα τα επεισόδια BSI που προκλήθηκαν από CR *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (CRKP), CR *Acinetobacter baumannii* (CRAB), CR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (CRPA), ανθεκτικά στη βανκομυκίνη στελέχη *Enterococcus spp* (VRE) και ανθεκτικό στη μεθικιλίνη *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA). Η ταυτοποίηση έγινε με συμβατικές ή αυτοματοποιημένες μεθόδους (Vitek 2 Compact, bioMerieux). Ο έλεγχος ευαισθησίας στα αντιμικροβιακά και ο προσδιορισμός των τιμών MIC πραγματοποιήθηκε με το Vitek 2 ή/και Etest (bioMerieux).

Καταγράφηκαν 395 επεισόδια BSI που προκλήθηκαν από τα παθογόνα της μελέτης με μέση ετήσια επίπτωση 21,21/1000 PD. Η επίπτωση ελαττώθηκε από 22,95/1000 PD το 2011 σε 17,90/1000 PD το 2013, όμως, το 2014 παρατηρήθηκε στατιστικά σημαντική αύξηση (25,21/1000 PD, $p=0,03$). Δεν βρέθηκε συσχέτιση μεταξύ της κατανάλωσης αντιμικροβιακών και της επίπτωσης. Τα προεξάρχοντα παθογόνα ήταν τα CRAB και CRKP. Η χρήση αντιβιοτικών ήταν υψηλή και στα 5 έτη της μελέτης, με μέση ετήσια κατανάλωση 3077 DDD/1000 PD. Το συνηθέστερα συνταγογραφούμενο αντιβιοτικό ήταν η αμπικιλίνη/σουλμπακτάμη (17,7%), ακολουθούμενη από τη μεροπενέμη (16,8%) και την κολιστίνη (11,8%). Η συνολική κατανάλωση αυξήθηκε κατά 20,3% μεταξύ των ετών 2010 και 2014 ($p=0,18$). Το ποσοστό μεταβολής στη χρήση αντιβιοτικών ήταν πιο αξιοσημείωτο για τις κινολόνες (128,4%, $p=0,004$) και την κολιστίνη (66,1%, $p=0,02$). Τάση μείωσης παρατηρήθηκε για λίγα μόνο αντιβιοτικά, όπως η τιγκεκυκλίνη (-48,5%, $p=0,12$) και η νταπτομυκίνη (-93%, $p=0,012$). Η συνολική κατανάλωση ελαττώθηκε, παροδικά, το 2011 (-21,3%, $p=0,33$) και κατόπιν σημειώθηκε συνεχής και στατιστικά σημαντική αύξηση ($p=0,022$).

Συμπερασματικά η τοπική επιδημιολογία της αντοχής καθορίζει σε μεγάλο βαθμό τις θεραπευτικές αποφάσεις. Στο νοσοκομείο μας, αλλά και στη χώρα μας, η υψηλή επίπτωση των CRGN συνήθως επιβάλλει τη χρήση αντιβιοτικών ευρέως φάσματος και τελευταίας γραμμής. Στην εποχή της αυξανόμενης αντοχής και των περιορισμένων θεραπευτικών επιλογών, η ορθολογική χρήση αντιβιοτικών είναι ζωτικής σημασίας. Τα δεδομένα επιτήρησης που αναλύσαμε αυξάνουν την ευαισθητοποίηση μας και καθιστούν επιβεβλημένη την εφαρμογή προγραμμάτων ΕΚΟΧΑ, για τη βελτιστοποίηση της συνταγογράφησης και τη διαφύλαξη της αποτελεσματικότητας των αντιβιοτικών τελευταίας γραμμής.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

κατανάλωση αντιβιοτικών, ορθολογική χρήση αντιβιοτικών, επιτήρηση, πολυανθεκτικά παθογόνα, αντοχή στις καρβαπενέμες

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